

IT Profile Authentication System by peer and expert validation techniques.

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Abstract

Keywords:

1. Introduction

Using a variation of Blockchain concept to validate IT Profiles and skills by Peer and Expert

2. Aim

To validate both experience and skills of IT candidates.

3. Material and methods

Integration of Blockchain and Bayes concepts to validate by assessing previous evidences

4. Results

We have made a significant progress in authenticating the profiles and skills for TalentAccurate in phase 1 & 2. Other phases are in the pipeline.

5. Conclusions

Candidate profiles will be authenticated by Peers, Experts and our Algorithms. If candidate fakes in future, it will be easily identified

6. Keywords

Bayes Chain; Blockchain; Experience Archive; Candidate Profile Authentication;

Author biography

Raja CSP Raman Raja CSP Raman, has been in the IT industry for 13 years in Telecom, Ecommerce & Gaming industries, mainly concentrated on Web application architectures, scaling and performance.

He authored a book called "Building RESTful Web Services with Spring 5". Also, he is the founder of TalentAccurate - where employers hire IT candidates without Resume.

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